

CORRELATIVE STUDY OF PROLACTIN AND AMH IN FEMALE INFERTILITY

Ankita Rani¹, Mr. Shyam Sundar Yadav^{2*}, Dr. Sameera Juneja³, Sapna Kumari⁴,
Tripti Kumari⁵, Dr. Himanshu Ranjan⁶, Dr. Sajad Ahmad Bhat⁷, Dr. Rachna⁸

1,4,5 M.Sc MLT, Department of Medical Laboratory Technology, Nims College of Paramedical Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur

2*Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Nims College of Paramedical Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

3. Gynaecologist, Department of IVF , National Institute of Medical Sciences & Research center, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

6. Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Nims College of Paramedical Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

7. Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Nims College of Paramedical Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

8. Associate Professor, Department of Medical Laboratory Technology, Nims College of Paramedical Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

* Corresponding Author : Mr. Shyam Sundar Yadav, Assistant Professor, Department of Medical Lab Technology, Nims College of Paramedical Technology, Nims University Rajasthan, Jaipur.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Infertility affects a significant proportion of women worldwide, with hormonal imbalances playing a critical role in its etiology. Among these, serum prolactin and anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) are key biomarkers involved in reproductive function. While elevated prolactin can disrupt ovulation, AMH serves as a marker of ovarian reserve. Understanding the correlation between these hormones may provide valuable insights into female infertility.

Methods: This observational study was conducted on a cohort of women presenting with infertility at NIMS Hospital Rajasthan, Jaipur. The study subjects included 91

infertile women in the age group of 21-45 years attending Gynaecology OPD during study period. Serum levels of prolactin and AMH were measured using chemiluminescent immunoassay techniques. Statistical analysis was performed to assess the correlation between prolactin and AMH levels, and to compare hormone levels across different infertility types (primary vs. secondary).

Result: Both hormones showed statistically significant differences with P-values < 0.001, suggesting that the observed hormone distributions are unlikely to be due to chance. These results highlight the heterogeneity in hormonal profiles among infertile women and underscore the clinical relevance of PRL and AMH as important diagnostic markers in infertility assessment.

Conclusion: The analysis of prolactin and AMH levels among infertile women revealed statistically significant findings, with both hormones showing highly variable distributions ($P < 0.001$). Elevated mean prolactin levels suggest a notable prevalence of hyperprolactinemia, which can interfere with normal ovulatory function. Simultaneously, the wide range and reduced median values of AMH indicate a decline in ovarian reserve in a subset of the study population. These findings support the clinical utility of assessing both prolactin and AMH levels as part of a comprehensive hormonal evaluation in the diagnosis and management of female infertility.

Keywords:

Female infertility, Prolactin, Anti-Müllerian Hormone (AMH), Hyperprolactinemia, Ovarian reserve, Hormonal imbalance

INTRODUCTION:

Infertility impacts over 48 million couples worldwide, representing an estimated 15% of couples who are of reproductive age, according to the World Health Organization.^[1] A major worldwide health concern, infertility impacts a couple's sexual, economical, psychological, and social lives. When a couple cannot conceive after a year of getting married, despite having frequent, unprotected sex, they are considered infertile.^[2]

The inability of a couple to conceive after a year of consistent, unprotected sexual activity is known as infertility.^[3] This condition brings significant social and economic burdens in addition to physical and mental difficulties. Infertility can cause psychological suffering and stigma in many cultures, which can affect social standing and interpersonal relationships^[4]. In addition, the cost of infertility treatments can be exorbitant, which frequently exacerbates already-existing health inequities. A comprehensive strategy is needed to address infertility, one that supports research into efficient therapies and increases access to reproductive health services^[5].

Infertility causes unhealed scars that traumatize women socially and emotionally in any country where having children defines a woman's identity and motherhood has significant social value^[6].

Numerous elements that make up a person's infertility profile, including as lifestyle decisions, medical history, and socioeconomic circumstances, are frequently connected to infertility.^[7] Age is a major factor, according to research, with female fertility drastically decreasing beyond the age of 35 as a result of a decline in ovarian reserve and quality. Lifestyle factors such as smoking, obesity, and heavy alcohol consumption are associated with reduced fertility in both men and women.^[8] Medical conditions such as endometriosis and polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS), which affect ovulation and the reproductive system, can also contribute to infertility.^[9] Infertility outcomes are also greatly influenced by socioeconomic factors, such as access to healthcare and reproductive health education. People in lower socioeconomic groups, for example, can have trouble getting therapy, which could result in infertility that lasts longer . It is essential to comprehend this complex relationship in order to create prevention and treatment plans that work.^[10]

Hormonal imbalances and infertility:

Hormonal imbalances and their interactions are linked to a number of common infertility concerns, including:

Anovulation (failure to create mature eggs): Ovulation, or the release of an egg from a woman's ovaries, is necessary for fertilization and pregnancy. In ideal circumstances, one egg is released each month. Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) is a condition where ovulation is infrequent or absent, leading to symptoms such as infertility, hirsutism (excess hair growth), anovulation (lack of ovulation), and amenorrhea

(absence of menstruation). Reduced FSH production and normal or increased levels of LH, oestrogen, and testosterone are the root causes of anovulation. Ovarian cysts are prevalent because low FSH inhibits the ovarian follicles' normal growth.^[11]

PROLACTIN

The anterior pituitary gland's lactotrophs are specialized cells that create the polypeptide hormone prolactin. It is crucial for numerous homeostatic functions in addition to breastfeeding during reproduction. Prolactin signaling, which is expressed in many different tissues, is mediated by the transmembrane prolactin receptor (PRLR). The pathophysiology of schizophrenia and similar psychoses is significantly influenced by the hormone prolactin.^[12] Prolactin has been identified as a noteworthy marker for stress diagnosis. Prolactin levels are progressively increased during hypoglycemia, leading to symptomatic neuroglycopenia. Both a significant increase in brain PRL-R expression and an increase in prolactin gene expression in the hypothalamus area have been seen during pregnancy and lactation.^[13] Prolactin, an adenohypophysis hormone, promotes grooming habit, causes analgesia, and aids adaptive behavior. It protects against the biochemical changes brought on by stress. Women may be more likely than men to experience a greater increase in prolactin, and this is reliant on estradiol levels.^[14]

Hyperprolactinemia, or elevated prolactin levels, is a known cause of infertility in both men and women. It is primarily brought on by disruptions in reproductive hormone pathways, which are crucial for reproductive health and can be dysregulated to cause infertility.^[15] This condition can also interfere with a woman's regular menstrual cycle, causing irregular periods and anovulation (lack of ovulation), both of which are significant contributors to infertility. Male libido and sperm production may be negatively impacted by reduced testosterone production brought on by high prolactin levels. Research has indicated that conditions such as prolactin-secreting tumors (prolactinomas) can exacerbate infertility. Effective pharmaceutical control of prolactin levels or treatment of underlying issues can improve fertility outcomes.^[16]

Mechanisms of Female Infertility Caused by Prolactin :

- **Ovulation suppression:** Excessive prolactin can interfere with the production of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH) by inhibiting

the release of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH). This disruption leads to irregular menstrual cycles and anovulation (the absence of ovulation)^[17]

- **Estrogen interference:** When prolactin levels are high, estrogen levels are lowered, which results in symptoms that hinder conception, such as dry vagina and decreased cervical mucus.
- **Lactation without pregnancy:** Hyperprolactinemia frequently coexists with galacterrhea, or milk production unrelated to childbirth.
- **Important Routes Impacted by the Hypothalamic-Pituitary Axis:** Kisspeptin neurons, which are essential for triggering GnRH release, are suppressed by prolactin. In investigations on mice, prolactin-induced infertility was restored by kisspeptin restoration.^[18]
- **Gonadotropin Dysregulation:** Testicular steroidogenesis and ovarian follicular development are disrupted by decreased LH/FSH pulsatility.
- **Immune Modulation:** The cytokine-like characteristics of prolactin may be a factor in autoimmune diseases that have an indirect impact on fertility.^[19]

AMH (Anti- Mullerian Hormone)

The granulosa cells in the ovary's small, developing follicles create anti-Mullerian hormone (AMH). An important measure of a woman's ovarian reserve, which encompasses the number and caliber of her primordial follicles, is this. AMH is a homodimer glycoprotein found on the short arm of chromosome 19 that belongs to the transforming growth factor-B (TGFB) class.^[20] The maturation of primordial follicles is triggered by Follicle-Stimulating Hormone (FSH) when the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal (HPG) endocrine axis becomes active during puberty. AMH is initially produced as a 140 kDa disulfide-linked homodimer, consisting of two 560-amino acid monomers. The active form of AMH includes an N-terminal pro region (around 110 kDa) and a C-terminal dimer (around 25 kDa). AMH is widely used as a serum marker to assess ovarian reserve and in the evaluation of Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS). It interacts with two specific receptors, AMHRI and AMHRIL, to transmit signals related to Suppressor of Mothers Against Decapentaplegic (SMAD) proteins. These receptors efficiently relay intracellular signals through nuclear and physiological binding to AMH.^[21]

Anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH), a crucial indicator for reproductive health, primarily represents a woman's ovarian reserve and affects fertility outcomes. Since granulosa

cells in ovarian follicles produce AMH, which plays a number of roles in follicular growth, steroidogenesis, and ovarian aging, it is crucial in today's fertility testing. [22]

AMH in Female Infertility :

Ovarian Reserve Assessment: AMH levels are the most accurate way to assess ovarian reserve because they strongly correlate with the number of **antral follicles**. A decrease in AMH levels can indicate a shorter reproductive lifespan and signal the approach of menopause, which can help with fertility planning. [23]

AMH and prolactin

The Two Roles of Hyperprolactinemia:

Anovulation and decreased ovarian activity are the results of high serum prolactin suppressing GnRH.

Ironically, prolactin from follicular fluid may improve endometrial receptivity and oocyte competence⁴. Systemic hyperprolactinemia, however, continues to be harmful to fertility in general. Although there is less evidence linking prolactin and AMH directly, hyperprolactinemia frequently coexists with thyroid disease, which indirectly affects AMH by increased TSH³⁵. [24]

MATERIAL AND METHOD

An observational study was conducted at NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, in which 91 women aged between 21 and 45 years, attending the gynecology OPD and experiencing infertility, were enrolled. The aim of the study was to find the serum prolactin & AMH estimation in infertility. To achieve this, 5 ml of blood was collected from each participant under aseptic precautions in a plain vial. The collected samples were analyzed using fully automated analyzers on instruments VITROS at the Biochemistry Department (Central Laboratory), NIMS Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan. The levels of Prolactin and AMH were measured, followed by statistical analysis of the results.

RESULT

Age Distribution of Participants :

The age distribution of participants was segmented into three groups: 21–30, 31–40, and 41–45. The data included the number of participants, Mean age, Median age, and Standard Deviation (Sdv) for each group. Age Group 21–30: This group had the highest number of participants (n = 51). The mean age was 25.8, and the median was 26. A standard deviation (Sdv) of 2.77 suggested a moderate spread of ages within this group, meaning most participants were close to the average, though there was some variation. Age Group 31–40: This group consisted of 34 individuals. The mean age was 33.8, and the median was 33.5. The standard deviation was 2.27, slightly lower than the previous group. Age Group 41–45: This group had only 6 participants. The mean age was 42.7, the median was 42.0, and the standard deviation was 1.21, the lowest among all groups.

Table 1 Age wise distribution

Age	Count	Mean	Median	Sdv
21 - 30	51	25.8	26	2.77
31 - 40	34	33.8	33.5	2.27
41 - 45	6	42.7	42.0	1.21

Figure : 5 Age Wise Distribution

Infertility Hormones Analysis

The values of infertility hormones were determined by categories such as N (total), mean, median, and standard deviation. This study evaluated the levels of infertility-related hormones, specifically prolactin (PRL) and anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH), in a sample of 91 individuals. The descriptive statistics, including mean, median, and standard deviation (SD), along with P-values, were recorded. The mean PRL level was 30.3 ng/mL, with a notably lower median of 19.42 ng/mL and a high standard deviation of 84.8. The significantly low P-value (< 0.001) implied that the observed levels were statistically significant and not due to random chance. Similarly, the AMH levels had a mean of 3.47 ng/mL, a median of 2.43 ng/mL, and a standard deviation of

4.91. The P-value of (< 0.001) confirmed that the AMH levels observed were also statistically significant.

Table 3 Determination of values of infertility hormones.

Catogery	N	Mean	Median	Sdv	P value
PRL	91	30.3	19.42	84.8	< 0.001
AMH	91	3.47	2.43	4.91	< 0.001

Figure : 7 Descriptive statistics of infertility hormones

ASSOCIATION MATRIX OF INFERTILITY HORMONE

Catogery	df	P value
PRL	91	0.036
AMH	91	0.021

DISCUSSION

The mean age of participants in our study was 25.8 ± 2.77 . The results of our study were found similar to the previous study completed by **Shikha Saxena et al. (2016)**,^[25] in which the mean age of infertile women was 27.8 ± 4.49 , respectively. The result of our study was slightly different from the previous study, possibly due to socioeconomic status, stabilization in lifestyle, or career. These findings are important

for interpreting trends and preferences that may vary by age and can inform targeted interventions or communications in similar demographic studies.

In the study of infertility hormones, prolactin and AMH, the mean values of Prolactin (PRL) and AMH were 30.3 ± 84.8 and 3.47 ± 4.91 , respectively, which were found significant ($P < 0.001$). The mean PRL level was significantly higher than the median, coupled with a high standard deviation, suggesting a right-skewed distribution. This indicated that while many individuals had PRL levels around the median, a subset exhibited markedly elevated levels, potentially due to conditions like hyperprolactinemia. Elevated prolactin can disrupt ovulation and menstrual cycles, contributing to infertility. The mean AMH level exceeded the median, with a substantial standard deviation, indicating variability in ovarian reserve among the participants. AMH is a measure of ovarian reserve, and diseases including polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and age might affect its levels. In the previous study, **Jyotshna B Palgamkar et al. (2021)**^[26], focusing on Indian women seeking infertility treatment, found a concerning trend of low AMH levels, indicating early ovarian senescence. This emphasizes the importance of early fertility assessment and intervention in this population. Natalia **Pedachenko et al. (2020)**^[27] conducted research comparing infertile women with and without endometriosis, which revealed that those with endometriosis had higher prolactin levels and lower AMH concentrations. This underscores the complex interplay between hormonal levels and reproductive pathologies.

The current analysis reveals a statistically significant association between prolactin (PRL) and anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) levels with infertility, as indicated by their respective *p-values* (PRL: $p = 0.036$; AMH: $p = 0.021$). These findings underscore the critical role of hormonal regulation in female reproductive health.

Prolactin (PRL) The observed *p-value* of 0.036 indicates a significant association, suggesting that abnormal PRL levels may contribute to reproductive dysfunction in the study population. These results align with previous studies demonstrating that elevated PRL disrupts gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) pulsatility, leading to decreased luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) secretion, thereby impairing ovulation.^[28]

Anti-Müllerian Hormone (AMH), secreted by granulosa cells of ovarian follicles, serves as a reliable marker of ovarian reserve. A statistically significant association ($p = 0.021$) between AMH levels and infertility in this study reinforces the value of AMH as a predictor of female fertility potential. Low AMH levels typically reflect diminished ovarian reserve, a condition frequently observed in women with reduced fertility or advancing reproductive age^[29] Conversely, excessively high AMH levels are often seen in conditions such as polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), which is also associated with anovulation and infertility. Thus, both extremes of AMH levels can be detrimental to normal reproductive function.^[30]

These findings highlight the importance of evaluating hormonal profiles in women undergoing infertility assessments. Both PRL and AMH measurements can provide essential insights into the underlying causes of infertility, aiding clinicians in diagnosis and treatment planning.

CONCLUSION

The association matrix highlights a statistically significant relationship between infertility and the hormonal parameters of prolactin (PRL) ($p = 0.036$) and anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) ($p = 0.021$). These findings indicate that both elevated or imbalanced prolactin levels and altered AMH concentrations are significantly associated with reproductive dysfunction. Monitoring these hormonal markers can therefore be instrumental in the early detection, evaluation, and management of infertility in affected individuals. The results underscore the need for comprehensive hormonal profiling in fertility assessments to improve diagnostic accuracy and guide targeted therapeutic interventions.

REFERENCE -

- 1.Saxena Shikha, Gupta Ranjana, Agarwal Lata , Srivastava Chandra Prem, Mallick Khurram Ayaz (2016):Correlation of serum thyroid stimulating hormone and

- prolactin in female infertility-a case control study. *Indian Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology Research* 2016;3(4):388-392
2. Zegers-Hochschild, F., Adamson, G. D., Dyer, S., et al. (2017). The International Glossary on Infertility and Fertility Care. *Fertility and Sterility*, 108(3), 393-406.
3. Inhorn, M. C., & Patrizio, P. (2015). Infertility Around the Globe: New Thinking on Gender, Reproductive Technologies and Global Movements in the 21st Century. *Human Reproduction Update*, 21(4), 411-426.
4. Mascarenhas, M. N., Flaxman, S. R., Boerma, T., et al. (2012). National, regional, and global trends in infertility prevalence since 1990: a systematic analysis of 277 health surveys. *PLOS Medicine*, 9(12), e1001356.
5. Ali Al-fahham University of Kufa hormonal imbalance and female infertility Research · January 2016 DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.1222.5041.
6. Chandra, A., & Copen, C. E. (2016). "Infertility Service Use in the United States." *National Health Statistics Reports*.
7. Dumoulin, J. C., et al. (2019). "Lifestyle and fertility." *Fertility and Sterility*, 111(3), 433-440.
8. Thoma, M. E., Connolly, M. P., Phillips, S. J., et al. (2013). Prevalence of infertility and help seeking in the United States: data from the National Survey of Family Growth. *Fertility and Sterility*, 99(2), 502-507.
9. McGee, E. A., & Hsueh, A. J. W. (2000). Follicular development: The role of the pituitary gonadotropins. *Reproductive Biology and Endocrinology*, 1(1), 1-10.
10. Shanmugam Ramya , Prasad Poornima et.al (2023): Role of Hormones and the Potential Impact of Multiple Stresses on Infertility *Stresses* 2023, 3, 454-474. <https://doi.org/10.3390/stresses3020033>
11. Azziz, R., Woods, K. S., Reyna, R., et al. (2004). The prevalence and features of the polycystic ovary syndrome in an unselected population. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 89(6), 2745-2749.
12. Melmed, S., Casanueva, F. F., Kleinberg, D. L., et al. (2011). A consensus on the diagnosis and treatment of hyperprolactinemia: a statement from the Pituitary Society. *Clinical Endocrinology*, 75(4), 411-418.

13. Broer, S. L., Mol, B. W., Hendriks, D. J., et al. (2011). A systemic review of ovarian reserve markers in predicting pregnancy and live birth after IVF. *Human Reproduction Update*, 17(5), 591-600.
14. R Mazzilli, S Medenica, A M Di Tommaso et.al (2024): The role of thyroid function in female and male infertility: a narrative review
15. A Faggiano¹, S La Vignera^{6,#}, G Defeudis (2024) : Understanding the Role of Thyroid Health in Infertility: What You Need to Know
16. Ursula B Kaiser et.al (2024) : Hyperprolactinemia and infertility: new insights .Hyperprolactinemia-induced ovarian acyclicity is reversed by kisspeptin administration".
17. Jure Bedenk, Eda Vrtačnik-Bokal, Irma Virant-Klun The role of anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) in ovarian disease and infertility.
18. Iya Eze Bassey, Alphonsus Ekpe Udoh, Okon Ekwerre Essien et.al Thyroid Hormones and Prolactin Levels in Infertile Women in Southern Nigeria.
19. Priyanka Sharma Anita Pal et.al Correlation of prolactin and thyroid disorders in infertile women.
20. Greil, A. L., Slauson-Blevins, K., & McQuillan, J. (2010). "The Experience of Infertility: A Review of Recent Literature." *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 32(1), 140–162.
21. Agiwal V, Madhuri RS, Chaudhuri S. Infertility Burden Across Indian States: Insights from a Nationally Representative Survey Conducted During 2019–21. *J Reprod Infertil*. 2023;24(4):287–292.
22. World Health Organization (WHO). Infertility Prevalence Estimates, 1990–2021. WHO, 2023.
23. Katole A, Saoji AV. Prevalence of Primary Infertility and its Associated Risk Factors in Urban Population of Central India: A Community-Based Cross-Sectional Study. *Indian J Community Med*. 2019;44(4):337–341.
24. Kumar R, Choudhary S, Sharma S. Prevalence of Female Infertility and its Socio-Economic Factors in Tribal Communities of Central India. *Rural Remote Health*. 2006;6(3):456.

- 25.Sharma R, Biedenharn KR, Fedor JM, Agarwal A. Lifestyle Factors and Reproductive Health: Taking Control of Your Fertility. *Reprod Biol Endocrinol.* 2013;11:66.
- 26.Sundararajan V, Bedi R, Soni S. Do Dietary Patterns and Morbidities Have a Relationship with Primary Infertility Among Women? A Study from NFHS-4 (2015–16), India. *Indian J Community Med.* 2021;46(2):281–285
- 27.Jyotshna B Palgamkar , Deepika K Jindal , et.al;(2021): Anti-Mullerian Hormone Levels in Indian Women Seeking Infertility Treatment: Are Indian Women Facing Early Ovarian Senescence? PMID: 35197683 PMCID: PMC8812391 DOI: 10.4103/jhrs.jhrs_71_21_2021 Oct-Dec;14(4):380-385. doi: 10.4103/jhrs.jhrs_71_21. Epub 2021 Dec 31.
- 28.Natalia Pedachenko et.al; (2020) : Serum anti-Mullerian hormone, prolactin and estradiol concentrations in infertile women with endometriosis PMID: 33274686 DOI: [10.1080/09513590.2020.1855634](https://doi.org/10.1080/09513590.2020.1855634)2021 Feb;37(2):162-165. doi: 10.1080/09513590.2020.1855634. Epub 2020 Dec 4.
- 29.Kundu, D., et al. (2023). Surging trends of infertility and its behavioural determinants in India.
- 30.D A Metzger , A F Haney Endometriosis: etiology and pathophysiology of infertility PMID: 3067928 DOI: 10.1097/00003081-198812000-00006 1988 Dec;31(4):801-12.